

Garhwal's Path to Sustainability: Land Rehabilitation through Traditional Agroforestry

¹Tanya Singh, ²Dr. Rituja Sharma

¹Research Scholar, Department of Legal Studies, Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India.
Email: tnsingh0891@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Department of Legal Studies, Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India.
Email: dr.ritujasharma@gmail.com

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Abstract

Land rehabilitation, also known as land restoration or land reclamation, is the process of restoring or improving the quality, health, and productivity of degraded, damaged, or otherwise impaired land. This degradation can result from various human activities or natural processes, such as deforestation, mining, urbanization, overgrazing, improper agricultural practices, industrial pollution, and climate change. Land rehabilitation through traditional agroforestry practices in the Garhwal district of India represents an excellent approach to sustainable land use and environmental restoration. Agroforestry helps in water regulation, reducing runoff and enhancing groundwater recharge, which is vital for sustainable agricultural practices. Traditional agroforestry provides additional sources of income for farmers, especially in areas where agriculture is the primary livelihood. It also contributes to poverty alleviation and community development. The Garhwal district, located in the state of Uttarakhand, is known for its rugged terrain, diverse flora and fauna, and a strong cultural heritage deeply intertwined with traditional agricultural practices. This study dwells into studying the various the traditional agroforestry practices in Garhwal such as Agnihotra Farming System, Taungya System, Silvopastoral System etc. and their potential towards conserving biodiversity. It further addresses the various challenges such as the lack of awareness and knowledge about the benefits of traditional agroforestry, the limited resources available in Garhwal region, both financial and technical, for implementing agroforestry practices. While organizing awareness campaigns, educational programs to educate farmers about the advantages of agroforestry can become useful; the same may remain inadequate without facilitating partnerships between government agencies, NGOs, and local communities to pool resources and expertise for effective implementation.

Keywords: Climate Change, Rehabilitation, Land Mitigation, Garhwal, Traditional, Agroforestry

1. Introduction

In every continent across the globe, climate change has significantly affected the social and natural systems. It will also have an impact on the dominant behaviors and interactions of different processes within interacting systems and sub-systems (Field, 2014). Predominantly, climate change is caused due to global warming, which is brought on by an increase in greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere. The presence of carbon dioxide, one of the main greenhouse gases, traps solar energy in the atmosphere and keeps it from escaping into space. As a result of this phenomenon, the global temperature rises, which affects many systems including sea level rise, glacier melting, and changes in the global climate pattern. Climate change is causing significant changes to the agricultural system, primarily resulting in a 10–20% reduction in agricultural productivity for food production (Gerald C. Nelson, 2009). This is proving hazardous for food security in several parts of the world, particularly the developing nations (Field, 2014).

The probable effects of climate change have been long recorded by several scholars. The most notable challenges are most to agricultural patterns (Bureau, 2003). According to Recha, a rise in climate change will increase the water requirement of crops in order to meet the increased evaporation and transpiration demands; reduce the quantity of groundwater available to plants; expedite the degradation of land resource due to soil erosion; pose new challenges due to the use of pesticides; and affect the community's ability to invest in agriculture activities due to extreme weather conditions posed by climate change (Recha, 2014). The impact of climate change on Indian agriculture has proven detrimental to the interests of farmers and put them at the risk of vulnerability. Climate change poses greater risks to agriculture productivity in India, a developing nation where Indian farmers prominently rely upon the monsoon rains for irrigation. Since rainfed agriculture makes up two thirds of India's agricultural land and even irrigated agriculture depends on monsoon rain, the country's agriculture is particularly vulnerable to the risks associated with climate change, particularly drought. Mountains, the home to a variety of natural ecosystems, ensure the existence of their inhabitants in many different ways, including by providing food, shelter, air, water, and many other necessities. In India, Himalayan region serves as the home to a distinctive blend of flora and fauna that nourish and replenish farmlands and other ecosystems while offering a range of essential ecosystem services that enable the local population to survive. The communities residing in the Himalayas have historically utilized a broad range of forest resources and products. However, owing to anthropogenic pressure, deforestation, and ecosystem degradation, agroforestry practices within traditional farming systems have garnered increased attention for their multifunctional role and ecosystem service dynamics in international agreements, policymaking, and research.

Land rehabilitation plays a crucial role in mitigating and adapting to climate change. Climate change is resulting in various environmental challenges such as increased temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, extreme weather events, and sea-level rise. These changes can have significant impacts on ecosystems,

biodiversity, and the livelihoods of communities dependent on the land. In traditional societies, local cultures are reinforced by their close ties to the natural environment that supports them, and sustainable natural resource management is shaped by the attitudes and actions of human communities (Stephan Rist, 2003). Traditional cultures don't differentiate between sacred and objective knowledge, and our modern world is frequently worse off as a result of scientific rationalism (Negi, 2005). However, traditional knowledge-based systems (TKBS) can only be considered valuable for conservation if they meet two fundamental requirements: they must be built with the intention of preventing or mitigating habitat degradation, species extinction, and resource depletion. This paper uses these two criteria as analytical tools to describe the traditional knowledge-based systems that mountain communities have developed and follow. With this, the inherent role of salient cultural practices, in particular the agroforestry practices, in Tehri Garhwal district is also looked into.

2. Setting the Background

2.1 Area of Study

Due to its delicate ecosystem, the Himalaya is still affected by human activity. The inhabitants of the Himalayan Mountains are endangering the natural landscape, making the disasters more likely. Therefore, land use studies are essential for the Himalayan region to monitor changes. In order to analyze the change in land cover and evaluate the role of agroforestry methods in climate change mitigation, this paper takes into account the demographic region of Garhwal region.

Primarily, there are two divisions in the state of Uttarakhand: Garhwal Division and Kumaon Division (Uttarakhand). Seven districts of Uttarakhand comprise Garhwal Himalaya, which is a portion of the western Himalaya (see Figure 1). These districts are (Uttarakhand G. o.):

- Haridwar
- Chamoli
- Dehradun
- Pauri Garhwal/Pauri
- Uttarkashi
- Tehri Garhwal/Tehri
- Rudraprayag.

It encompasses 33,412 km per square. The range of altitude is 195 m to 7,816 m asl. For the purpose of this study, Tehri Garhwal region has been chosen to draw various findings and conclusions. The study area's forest types include dry deciduous forest, moist deciduous forest, sal forest, pine forest, temperate and sub-alpine broadleaf forest, alpine scrub, and alpine pastures due to the vast differences in topography.

Figure 1 (Uttarakhand G. o.)

2.2 Need of Land Rehabilitation

Land rehabilitation, also known as land restoration or reclamation, involves restoring degraded land to a more productive, healthy, and sustainable state. World Health Organization has defined rehabilitation as “a set of interventions designed to optimize functioning and reduce disability in individuals with health conditions in interaction with their environment” (Organization, 2023). Tehri Garhwal, located in the Indian state of Uttarakhand, is known for its scenic landscapes, rich biodiversity, and cultural heritage. The need for land rehabilitation in Tehri Garhwal arises from various environmental and socio-economic factors. Tehri Garhwal's hilly terrain makes it prone to soil erosion, especially during heavy rains and deforestation. Land rehabilitation techniques such as afforestation and contour ploughing aid in soil stabilization and erosion prevention, which is critical for maintaining land fertility (Nebiyu Masebo, 2016). Proper land rehabilitation practices contribute to the conservation of water resources. By preventing soil erosion, these practices help maintain the health of rivers and streams, ensuring a sustainable supply of water for agriculture and other purposes.

In Tehri, the major issues regarding land rehabilitation and resettlement are due to the development projects especially the construction and operation of Tehri Dam (Ashish Vacchani, 2009). The construction of dams, such as the Tehri Dam, often necessitates significant land rehabilitation efforts to mitigate the environmental and social impacts associated with large-scale infrastructure projects. The construction of the Tehri Dam involved the creation of a reservoir, which led to the submergence of large areas of land. Land rehabilitation efforts in this context offer various measures to address the loss

of agricultural land, displacement of communities, and the impact on local ecosystems (B.K. Sinha, 2001). Studies have observed that the construction of dam has resulted in the displacement of communities living in the affected areas. Here, resettlement and rehabilitation programs become crucial components of land rehabilitation efforts. This involves providing affected communities with alternative housing, livelihood options, and infrastructure to help them rebuild their lives.

2.3 The Concept of Agroforestry

Agroforestry is often referred to as a broad, ecologically based system of managing natural resources aiming to enhance the social, economic, and environmental benefits by extending and sustaining production through the plantation of trees on the farms as well as agricultural landscape (S. Franzel, 2002). In agroforestry practices, different combinations of trees, crops, and animals are found in different temporal or spatial sequences. In simple words, traditional agroforestry means “trees in support of agriculture” (Olofson, 1983). To put it broadly, indigenous agroforestry is the coexistence of various crops and trees in a land and/or time, with the primary effect being the trees supporting agriculture and the secondary effect of attaining the benefits of the agricultural crops on the trees. However, it can be a little challenging to identify the secondary effect in indigenous agroforestry since in most of the situations; it appears that the trees are beneficial to the crops.

Agro-ecosystems are a class of ecosystems that includes indigenous agroforestry. An ecosystem is a framework that includes interactions among organisms and their unique environments that can be studied. Ecosystems are by definition open systems because they contain living organisms, and one of their characteristics is the ability to absorb energy from their surroundings and incorporate it into their much more intricate structures. One category of agroecosystems, known as simultaneous polycultures, includes indigenous agroforestry systems. The term 'indigenous agroforestry' was coined by Kass to mean and include intercropping, interplanting, intercultural, mixed cropping, and relay-planting patterns. It is likely possible to categorize concurrent polycultures into two types: simple and complex. The simple kind, which Kass handled in his own work, might only involve two or three crops. As in the situations where clearings of traditional shifting cultivators have an array of species that may range far into the double figures, it would seem extremely difficult to understand the ecological relations among species in simultaneous polycultures in complex systems.

2.4 Agroforestry systems in Garhwal

According to a survey conducted by Ram Gopal and R.S. Bali, three prominent agroforestry systems were recorded in Tehri Garhwal district namely Agri-silviculture, Agri-silvo-pastoral system (also known as Homegarden) and Silvipasture system. For documenting the agro-biodiversity in various traditional agroforestry systems, a survey was conducted between 1000 and 2000 a.m.s.l. in the Tehri Garhwal district (Uttarakhand) (Ram Gopal, 2017). During fieldwork, 25 percent of the households

were arbitrarily selected based on their ability to hold land, divided into three categories: small (1–5 nali); medium (6–10 nali); and large (>10 nali). The survey was carried out through field observation to document systems, interviews with the head of the household, and the village Pradhan. According to the survey, there were three prominent agroforestry systems in Tehri Garhwal district namely Agri-silviculture, Agri-silvo-pastoral system (also known as Homegarden) and Silvipasture system.

2.4.1 Agri-Silviculture system

This system is primarily made up of forest trees and agricultural crops, mostly growing on the hillsides surrounding the fields. This means that this system focuses on land-use management system that combines trees/ shrubs with agricultural crops in a mutually beneficial manner. The system specifically focuses on the combination of agriculture and silviculture (the cultivation of trees). In an agri-silviculture system, trees are intentionally integrated into agricultural landscapes to enhance overall productivity and sustainability. The trees in such systems may serve various purposes, including providing shade, windbreaks, habitat for organisms, improving the fertility soil, water conservation, and overall ecosystem health (Ram Gopal, 2017).

In Tehri, agri-silviculture practices within the broader framework of agroforestry have been employed to address various agricultural and environmental challenges. In this region, the majority of the tree species are found on the bunds, however, the trees could also be found in the middle and between agricultural fields occasionally. Table 1 (Kaushik, 2017) represents the various types of agri-silvi crops in Tehri.

Table 1: Crops in Agri-Silviculture of agriculture

Tree Species	Kharib season		Intermediate	Rabi Season	
	Cereal Crop	Pulses	Oiled crop	Cereal	Pulses
“ <i>Grewia optiva</i> ” (Bhimal)	“ <i>Zea mays</i> ” (maize)	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> ” (Bean)	“ <i>Glycine max</i> ” (Soybean)	“ <i>Triticum aestivu</i> ” (Bread Wheat)	“ <i>Lens culinaris</i> ” (Lentil)
“ <i>Celtis australis</i> (Mediterranean ” hackberry)	“ <i>Eleusine coracana</i> ” (finger millet)	“ <i>Vigna umbellate</i> ” (Rice Bean)	“ <i>Sesamum indicum</i> ” (Sesame)	“ <i>Hordeum vulgare</i> ” (Barley)	
“ <i>Ficus roxburghii</i> ” (Broad-leaf Fig)	“ <i>Echinochloa frumentacea</i> ” (Indian Barn yard Millet)	“ <i>Psophocarpus tetragonolabus</i> ” (Winged Bean)	“ <i>Brassica campestris</i> ” (Field Mustard)		

<p>“<i>Quercus leucotrichophora</i>” (Banj Oak)</p> <p>“<i>Bauhinia</i>” (Tapak Kuda/ Purple Bauhinia)</p>	<p>“<i>Amaranthus caudatus</i>” (Tassel Flower)</p>	<p>“<i>Dolichos lablab</i>” (Hyacinth bean)</p> <p>“<i>Vigna mungo</i>” (Black Gram)</p>			
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Source: Author

2.4.2 Agri-silvo-pastoral system (also known as home garden system)

The term ‘silvo’ denotes ‘tress’ and ‘pastoral’ or ‘pasture’ means ‘grass’. An agri-silvo-pastoral system is a type of agroforestry that combines agriculture (agri), silviculture (silvo), and pastoralism (pastoral) in an integrated approach of land-use. Under this system, agricultural crops, forest trees, livestock and pastures are integrated on the same land to maximize the synergies and benefits derived from each component (Ramana, 2009). Therefore, mathematically, the agri-silvi pastoral system can be represented as:

$$\text{“Agrisilvipastoral system= Agriculture + Forestry + Pasture + Livestock”}$$

In Tehri, under the agri-silvo-pastoral system, plants are classified into various strata such as (a) less than one meter height (Strata I); (b) one to three meter height (Strata II); (c) three to ten meter height (Strata III) and, (iv) ten to twenty meter height (Strata IV) (Ram Gopal, 2017). In the first strata bearing less than one meter height, vegetables and weed grass grown annual are found. This included the species of vegetables such as *Trichosanthes dioica* grown in both rabi season and kharib season (Ram Gopal, 2017). In second strata bearing crops between one to three meter height, ‘*Malus domestica*’ is grown at higher altitude and ‘*Musa paradisiaca*’, ‘*Vitisinifera*’, ‘*Punica granatum*’, ‘*Carica papaya*’ are grown in middle and lower mountain (Ram Gopal, 2017).

In the third strata bearing height between three to ten meter, various fruit plants and multipurpose tress such as ‘*Prunus persica*’, ‘*Prunus domestica*’, ‘*Prunus armeniaca*’, ‘*Pyrus communis*’, ‘*Citrus sinensis*’, ‘*Citrus aurantifolia*’ fruit trees are found at the higher altitude and ‘*Citrus reticulate*’, ‘*Annona squamosal*’, ‘*Annona reticulate*’, ‘*Psidium guajava*’, ‘*Embllica officinalis*’, ‘*Morus serrata*’ are grown in lower and middle altitude. In the fourth strata having crops between ten to twenty meter, ‘*Celtis australis*’, ‘*Juglans regia*’ are found in the higher altitude and ‘*Artocarpus heterophyllus*’ are located in lower altitude only (Ram Gopal, 2017). For the sake of clarity, the various crops grown under Agri-silvo-pastoral are documented in Table 2.

Table 2: Crops in Agri-Silvo-pastoral system

Strata I	Strata II	Strata III	Strata IV
Kharib Vegetables	Fruit Plants	Fruits and Multipurpose trees	Fruits and Multipurpose trees
<i>Pisum sativum</i> ”(Peas)	<i>“Musa paradisiaca”</i> (Banana)	<i>“Psidium guajava”</i> (Common Guava)	<i>“Celtis australis”</i> (Mediterranean hackberry)
<i>“Lycopersicon esculentum”</i> (Tomato)	<i>“Vitisvinifera”</i> (European Wine Grape)	<i>“Prunus persica”</i> (Peach)	<i>“Juglans regia”</i> (Persian Walnut)
<i>“Abelmoschus esculentus”</i> (Okra)	<i>“Punica granatum”</i> (Pomegranate)	<i>“Prunus domestica”</i> (Plum)	<i>“Artrocarpus heterophyllus”</i> (Jackfruit)
<i>Lagenaria siceraria”</i> (Bottle Gourd)	<i>“Carica papaya”</i> (Papaya)	<i>“Prunus armeniaca”</i> (Apricoat)	
<i>“Luffa acutangula”</i> (Ridged Gourd)	<i>“Malus domestica”</i> (Apple)	<i>“Prunus amygdalus”</i> (Almond)	
<i>“Momordica charantia”</i> (Bitter Gourd)		<i>“Pyrus communis”</i> (Common Pear)	
<i>“Cucumis sativus”</i> (Cucumber)		<i>“Emblica officinalis”</i> (Indian Gooseberry)	
<i>“Cucurbita maxima”</i> (Buttercup Squash)		<i>Citrus aurantifolia”</i> (West Indian Lime)	
<i>“Trichosanthes dioica”</i> (Pointed Gourd)		<i>“Citrus sinensis”</i> (Sweet Orange)	
<i>“Brassica oleracea var. capitata”</i> (Cabbage)		<i>“Citrus reticulate”</i> (Mandarian Orange)	
		<i>“Annona squamosal”</i> (Custard Apple)	

<p><i>“Brassica oleracea var. botrytis”</i> (Cauliflower)</p> <p><i>“Spinacea oleracea”</i> (Spinach)</p> <p><i>“Brassica juncea”</i>(Chinese Mustard)</p> <p><i>“Colocasia antiquorum”</i>(Taro)</p> <p><i>“Coriandrum sativum”</i> (Corriander)</p> <p><i>“Capsicum frutescens”</i> (Capsicum)</p> <p><i>“Zingiber officinale”</i> (Ginger)</p> <p><i>“Curcuma longa”</i> (Turmeric)</p> <p><i>“Allium cepa”</i> (Common Onion)</p>		<p><i>“Mangifera indica”</i> (Mango)</p> <p><i>“Morus serrate”</i> (Himalyan Mulberry)</p> <p><i>“Morus alba”</i> (White Mulberry)</p> <p><i>“Grewia oppositifolia”</i>(Bhimal)</p>	
Rabi season vegetables			
<p><i>“Capsicum annuum”</i> (Chilli)</p> <p><i>“Solanum tuberosum”</i> (Potato)</p> <p><i>“Raphanus sativus”</i> (Radish)</p>			

<p><i>“Daucus carota”</i> (Wild Carrot)</p> <p><i>“Coriandrum sativum”</i>(Cilantro)</p> <p><i>“Allium cepa”</i> (Common Onion)</p> <p><i>“Allium sativum”</i> (Garlic)</p>			
Grasses			
<p><i>“Andropogon munroi”</i> (Beard Grass)</p> <p><i>“Cynodon dactylon”</i> (Bermuda Grass)</p> <p><i>“Apluda mutica”</i> (Mauritian Grass)</p>			

Source: Author

2.4.3 Silvipasture system/ Silvipastoral System

Under this system, the same land is used to manage trees along with pasture and/or animals. Silvipasture is a specific type of agroforestry system that combines the cultivation of trees (silviculture) with pasture for livestock grazing (Ramana, 2009). Mathematically, silvipastoral system can be understood as:

$$\text{“Silvipastoral system= Forestry + Pasture + Livestock”}$$

In a silvipasture system, trees are intentionally integrated into pastures or rangelands to provide multiple benefits, including improved forage quality, enhanced animal welfare, and additional sources of income for landowners. This integrated approach aims to optimize the interactions between trees, forage, and livestock (Yadav, 2019).

In Tehri, a total of eleven varieties of trees, eleven varieties of shrubs, and five varieties of grasses are found under the silvipastoral system, on which the livestock unit grazes and browses (Ram Gopal, 2017). Table 3 displays the various crops and livestock under this system.

Table 3: Crops in Silvipasture System

Trees	Shurbs	Grass	Livestocks
“ <i>Ficus roxburghii</i> ” (Elephant Ear Tree)	“ <i>Rhus parviflora</i> ”(Tintideeka)	“ <i>Andropogon munroi</i> ” (Beard Grass)	“ <i>Andropogon munroi</i> ” (Beard Grass)
“ <i>Quercus leucotrichophora</i> ”(Banjh Oak)	“ <i>Rumex hastatus</i> ” (Arrowleaf Dock)	“ <i>Cynodon dactylon</i> ”(Bermuda Grass)	“ <i>Cynodon dactylon</i> ” (Bermuda Grass)
“ <i>Grewia oppositifolia</i> ” (Bhimal)	“ <i>Artemisia vulgaris</i> ” (Common Mugwort)	“ <i>Aplud mutica</i> ” (Mauritian Grass)	“ <i>Aplud mutica</i> ” (Mauritian Grass)
“ <i>Melia azedarach</i> ” (Chinaberry Tree)	“ <i>Eupatorium adenophorum</i> ” (Crofton Weed)	“ <i>Euphorbia hirta</i> ” (Asthma Plant)	“ <i>Euphorbia hirta</i> ” (Asthma Plant)
“ <i>Pinus roxburghii</i> ” (Chir Pine)	“ <i>Murraya koenigii</i> ” (Curry Leaf Tree)	“ <i>Avena fatua</i> ” (Wild Oat)	“ <i>Avena fatua</i> ” (Wild Oat)
“ <i>Ficus palmate</i> ” (The Punjab Fig)	“ <i>Berberis asiatica</i> ” (Indian Barberry)		
“ <i>Myrica esculenta</i> ” (Box Myrtle)	“ <i>Rubus ellipticus</i> ” (Yellow Himalayan Raspberry)		
“ <i>Cedrus deodara</i> ” (Himalayan Cedar)	“ <i>Rubus niveus</i> ” (Mysore Raspbberly)		
“ <i>Rhododendron arboretum</i> ” (Gurans)	“ <i>Desmodium elegans</i> ” (Elegant Tick Clover)		
“ <i>Toona ciliate</i> ” (Australian Redcedar)	“ <i>Rosa brunonii</i> ” Himalayan Musk Rose)		
“ <i>Pyrus pashia</i> ” (Wild Himalayan Pear)	“ <i>Indigofera gerardiana</i> ” (Himalayan Indigo)		

Source: Author

3. Agroforestry as a Cultural Expression

Indigenous Agroforestry, also known as integral social forestry is a practice that is deeply embedded in the cultural practices of a traditional community and forms an indispensable part of their survival (Olofson, 1983). It is a practice that is learned and acquired as a part of growing and belonging to a particular community. Many communities have practiced agroforestry for generations, incorporating specific trees, crops, and livestock that are culturally significant. These traditional practices often reflect a deep understanding of local ecosystems and are passed down through oral traditions and practical experience. Agroforestry systems contribute to the creation of unique cultural landscapes. The arrangement of trees, crops, and other elements in the landscape may be influenced by cultural beliefs, aesthetic preferences, and traditional knowledge, contributing to the identity of a community. This is because such practices often form part of traditional indigenous farming practices (Claudia de Brito Quadros Gonçalves, 2021).

Agroforestry often represents a cultural adaptation to the local environment. Communities develop agroforestry systems that are suited to their climate, soil conditions, and ecological surroundings, demonstrating a harmonious relationship between culture and nature. Certain trees or plants in agroforestry systems may hold spiritual or religious significance for a community. Agroforestry practices may be aligned with cultural rituals and ceremonies, reinforcing the spiritual connection between people and the land. In addition to developing food and medicines, indigenous agroforestry plays a vital part in the indigenous way of "living" within the traditional community, where the land is not viewed as private property but rather as a part of them (Nidia Catherine González, 2020). Agroforestry is also spiritually significant to indigenous peoples, who observe their community as a place where souls and spirits dwell. For that reason, these practices are much more important to their cultural survival than a method of cultivation. Consequently, there is a sense of responsibility for the environment since human beings will be affected by the effects of environmental degradation (Daniel Coq-Huelva, 2017).

Agroforestry practices are often associated with specific customs and festivals (Organization F. a.). For example, planting and harvesting seasons may coincide with cultural celebrations, marking important moments in the agricultural calendar. Such practices play a role in preserving traditional knowledge and practices. It is also observed that agroforestry management is influenced by a number of factors, including land ownership, agricultural intensification, and land use history. With this, ethnicity becomes an essential factor that impedes agroforestry practices and species diversity. Thus, observing and implementing an ethnic group's farming customs and traditions remain a prerequisite while implementing agroforestry systems in indigenous communities (Bolier Torres, 2018).

4. Agroforestry and Climate Change

Climate change has a substantial impact on human societies, ecosystems, and the climate system of Earth. The increase in global temperature, which is fueling the warming trend known as global warming, is the

most noticeable consequence of climate change (Nations). Heatwaves, extended duration of hot days per year, and rise in the average temperatures of Earth are the evident signs of global warming. Further, melting of glaciers and ice caps due to climate change has raised sea levels. The stability of polar ecosystems and the availability of freshwater resources are affected by this melting (Nations). Climate change is associated with an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, including storms, hurricanes, floods, droughts, and wildfires. These events can have disastrous effects on communities, ecosystems, and infrastructure. Frequency and distribution of rainfall are affected by deviations in precipitation patterns brought about by climate change. In certain areas, this may lead to longer and more severe droughts, while in other areas, it may lead to higher rainfall, which may exacerbate floods. The distribution of pests and diseases, growing seasons, and crop yields are all impacted by variations in temperature and precipitation patterns. The global food security may be significantly impacted by these effects (Luis Gustavo Barioni). The distribution and behavior of plant and animal species are impacted by climate change, which causes changes in ecosystems and a decline in biodiversity. The shifting habitats and environmental conditions can lead to the extinction of certain species. Temperature, precipitation, and sea level variations can upset ecosystems, impacting different species' migratory patterns, ability to reproduce, and chance of survival. Consequently, ecosystem services may experience a chain reaction of events.

There are several factors resulting to ecological transformation in the Himalayan region with climate change being the most prominent factor (see figure 2). High levels of overall climate change vulnerability are found in hill districts such as Tehri Garhwal, where agricultural vulnerability to the changing climate is on the rise (Research, 2021).

Figure 2: Factors resulting to Ecological Transformation in Himalayas (Maharaj K. Pandit, 2014)

Due to the deterioration of land quality brought on by climate change, migration has increased. ‘Climate

change-induced migration’ is the term used to describe the relocation of individuals or groups of people due to changes in the environment and the effects of climate change. According to a 2018 report of Rural Development and Migration Commission, Tehri remains on the higher rung of ladder to witness one of the highest percentage in migration owing to climate change (see Figure 3)

Table 7: District-wise migration destinations (%)

District	To Nearby Towns (%)	To District Headquarters (%)	To Other Districts (%)	Outside State (%)	Outside Country (%)
Uttarkashi	39.14	20.27	22.37	17.34	0.89
Chamoli	19.79	13.34	50.48	15.88	0.51
Rudraprayag	19.34	12.66	40.51	25.69	1.8
Tehri Garhwal	17.73	9.42	40.78	28.98	3.09
Dehradun	57.12	23.67	8.08	10.46	0.67
Pauri Garhwal	19.61	9.55	36.15	34.15	0.54
Pithoragarh	15.7	33.07	34.33	16.67	0.23
Bageshwar	15.45	22	37.19	25.18	0.19
Almora	7.13	13	32.37	47.08	0.43
Champawat	14	16.86	36.24	32.59	0.3
Nainital	35.49	17.93	21.47	24.64	0.47
Udham Singh Nagar	27.48	8.48	28.04	31.11	4.89
Haridwar	44.27	18.29	16.1	20.85	0.49

Source: Rural Development and Migration Commission, 2018

Figure 3: District wise percentage of migration (Locked Houses, Fallow Lands: Climate Change and Mitigation in Uttarakhand, India,)

The term Land Use indicates human use of land (Agency, Land Use, Report on the Environment). It refers to the outcome of environmental conservation efforts like afforestation, as well as, a cautionary system for actions that harm the environment. Land use analysis can identify activities like invasion, degrading the health or quality of the forest, and clearing of forest. There are several causes of land cover change, including human invasion and climate change.

In Tehri region, a significant shift in large-scale land is associated with the Tehri Hydro Power Project. The dam became operational since 2006 and has led to serious changes in the land cover of forest area, agricultural lands, scrubland, grasslands, etc. (see table 4)

Table 4: Change in Land Use in Tehri from 2000- 2020 (Seema Mehra Parihar, 2022)

Category	During 2000		During 2010		During 2020	
	Area (per km square)	% Area	Area (per km square)	% Area	Area (per km square)	% Area
Rivers, Lakes, Reservoirs	4.86	0.33	15.36	1.03	16.86	1.14
Agricultural Land	162.58	10.95	156.52	10.55	158.46	10.6
Sparse Woodland	127.32	8.58	147.61	9.95	152.23	10.25
Dense Woodland	776.42	52.31	691.71	46.61	775.85	52.26
Scrubland & Grasses	102.78	6.92	98.55	6.64	97.59	6.57
Resettlement	8.11	0.55	10.58	0.71	11.57	0.78

5. Land Rehabilitation and Climate Mitigation through Agroforestry

Agroforestry practiced for a long time by cultural communities inside their customary agricultural systems is known as indigenous agroforestry (Olofson, 1983). Due to its historical precedent and application by Westernized research scientists, it predates experimental agroforestry. Indigenous agroforestry is carried out in actual, functioning businesses within or close to farmers' fields, whereas "modern" agroforestry is still primarily restricted to experimental fields. According to the World Bank, agroforestry is a potential strategy for reducing vulnerability to climate change and helping subsistence farmers become more resilient (Derek Beyerlee, 2008). Biodiverse agro-ecological systems, like the tree-crop interaction on farms, are more resilient to extreme stresses. In addition to providing various environmental services to the impoverished farmers, agroforestry also diversifies the sources of income for these farmers.

The notion that indigenous communities were model conservationists first appeared in academic circles and popular media a few decades ago (Smith, 2006). Indigenous people's conservation philosophy has frequently been linked to their practical knowledge of and spiritual respect for nature. Evidence in support of this assessment is the comparatively higher biodiversity found in sacred forests, culturally expressed conservation ethics, and animistic religious beliefs that view other life forms as social beings (Bernbaum, 2006). Agroforestry systems' varied structural composition can increase an ecosystem's overall resilience towards climate change. There are several ways in which agroforestry methods have aided in land rehabilitation and climate mitigation in Tehri Garhwal. Some of these are discussed as follows:

- **Carbon Sequestration:** Trees perform an essential function of sequestering carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. Agroforestry contributes significantly to controlling the accumulation of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. Agroforestry systems in the humid and sub-humid tropical regions are estimated to have a carbon sequestration potential of less than 100 Mt CO year by 2030 to over

2000 Mt CO₂ year over a 30-year period (Verchot, 2007). Rehabilitating land can be one way to lessen the effects of climate change. Forests, for instance, help lower greenhouse gas levels by absorbing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. This can have a positive impact on local and global climate patterns. Agroforestry systems typically expropriate far more carbon than agricultural systems without trees (Wilkson Makumba, 2007) During photosynthesis, trees take in carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere, storing it in their biomass and soils. A significant amount of carbon is stored by agroforestry systems, which incorporate trees into agricultural landscapes and function as carbon sinks. This sequestration helps offset greenhouse gas emissions and contributes to the global effort to mitigate climate change.

- **Soil Conservation:** It has been observed that agroforestry practices can help in preventing soil erosion by providing ground cover through the trees and shrubs, particularly in areas where land degradation and desertification is a concern (Atangana, 2014). Through increasing water conservation, reducing soil erosion, boosting biodiversity, and sequestering carbon, agroforestry techniques can support environmental sustainability. Trees in agroforestry systems are a good source of increasing the organic matter in soil through leaf litter and root decomposition. This enhances soil fertility and nutrient content, promoting healthier and more productive soils for agriculture (Subhasis Mahato, 2016). Agroforestry offers an alternative form of land use that lessens the strain on natural forests. By incorporating trees into agricultural areas, less land must be cleared for farming or the production of lumber, which helps to stop deforestation and the release of carbon stored in the earth. The presence of trees in agroforestry systems increases the concentration of nutrients in the soil, which raises the soil's carbon content. This enhances soil fertility while also storing carbon in a stable form, which helps in mitigating the effects of climate change.
- **Long Term Sustainability:** Agroforestry in Tehri can promote sustainable land management by creating a resilient and diverse ecosystem. The combination of trees and crops can help maintain soil health, conserve water, and support sustainable agricultural practices over the long term. According to Dhyani, agroforestry is a vital pathway to profitability of millions of farming families, providing additional income, job creation, increased food and nutrient security, and sustainably meeting other basic human needs (S. K. Dhyani, 2009). As a strategy to mitigate climate change and restore degraded land, converting conventionally farmed agricultural crop land into agroforestry presents a significant opportunity. This is because agroforestry increases land productivity, aids in carbon sequestration, and prevents further soil degradation in terrace agriculture systems.

- **Water Conservation and Management:** Trees in agroforestry systems can contribute to improved water management. They help in regulating water flow, reducing the risk of floods and enhancing water infiltration into the soil. This is especially relevant in areas prone to water-related issues. Agroforestry provides shade to crops, reducing evaporation and water loss. This is particularly advantageous in dry and semi-arid areas where there is a risk of water scarcity. With this, the tree species under agroforestry systems prove effective in improving soil capacity in better retention of soil moisture (Avaneesh Kumar, 2020).
- **Providing Shelterbelts:** Windbreaks and shelterbelts are agroforestry practices that reduce wind velocity and thus limit erosion due to wind. Over-fertilizer contaminates water sources and lowers water quality when it is washed away from agricultural fields through surface runoff or leaches into the subsurface water supply. For instance, excessive sediment, fertilizers, and pesticides can be carried to receiving water bodies by agricultural surface runoff, which greatly increases the risk of eutrophication. Here, agroforestry systems aid in cleaning the runoff water by controlling the runoff velocity, promoting infiltration, sediment deposition, and nutrient preservation. Deep-rooted trees in agroforestry systems can also serve as a "safety net" by absorbing nutrients and enhancing the quality of ground water.

Overall, agroforestry systems with a variety of tree species encourage the preservation of biodiversity (Lindsey Norgrove, 2016). Increased biodiversity strengthens ecosystem resilience and may make ecosystems more resilient to changing weather patterns. Agroforestry systems' varied structural composition can increase an ecosystem's overall resilience to climate change. A system that is more complex and adaptive and can better withstand the effects of extreme weather events is one that includes trees, crops, and/or livestock. Agroforestry systems with trees can alter the microclimate by lowering temperature extremes and providing shade. This may increase the resilience towards climate variability and have an impact on productivity of cattle and crops.

6. Emerging Challenges to Agroforestry

Agroforestry is known to be one of the best traditional practices for reducing vulnerability and holds great potential in for sustainable land use. However, there are several challenges that need to be addressed to promote its widespread adoption. Availability of quality planting material, such as improved tree varieties and seedlings, can be a prominent challenge. Ensuring a consistent supply of high-quality planting material is crucial for the success of agroforestry initiatives (Pooja Verma, 2017). According to National Agroforestry Policy, 2014, nearly 10% of plantation material is of superior quality, with the remaining lacking any guarantee of quality. In addition, insufficient research has been done on agroforestry models for determining different varieties of agroclimatic zones, native species with multiple uses (like *Prosopis*

cineraria), or the domestication of species, which has led to an excessive focus on a select few species like Poplar, Eucalyptus, Kadam, and so forth.

Another alarming aspect is that agroforestry research in India is primarily undertaken at research stations with relatively small laboratories. The majority of studies were relatively short-term in nature, and there is little to no research conducted on the ecosystem or landscape level (S. Puri, 2004). Under such circumstances, the performance of agroforestry systems may be impacted by climate change, which includes extreme weather events, changed precipitation patterns, and rising temperatures. Except in a few states, the country lacks marketing infrastructure for agroforestry products. Consequently, it is primarily a buyer's market, with the middle-men enjoying a sizable profit. Given the lack of awareness on technical and economic data on various agroforestry models, institutional financing and insurance coverage in agroforestry have fallen short of their potential (Co-Operation, 2014). Access to funding for agroforestry initiatives may thwart investment in resources such as the quality of seed, irrigation infrastructure, and maintenance activities.

Establishing agroforestry systems often involves significant upfront costs. Planting trees, purchasing seeds or saplings, and preparing the land can require substantial financial investment. Further, Converting traditional agricultural land into an agroforestry system may require changes in land use and preparation, such as clearing existing vegetation, creating planting pits, or implementing contour bunds. These activities can be labor-intensive and costly which small and medium farmers may find challenging.

The efficient distribution of research findings on many facets of agroforestry depends on extension services; nevertheless, because there isn't a sufficient or focused system in place, farmers aren't regularly notified of the results of agroforestry research. Furthermore, farmers with large land holdings tend to benefit more from the various schemes related to agroforestry than the small and marginal farmers (Pooja Verma, 2017). Agroforestry adoption can be hampered by ambiguous or restrictive policies and regulations. Therefore, supportive policies that recognizes and promote agroforestry practices, such as land-use policies and regulations governing tree ownership and management, may be required.

7. Road Ahead

Agroforestry has the potential to play a critical role in climate change mitigation and adaptation. Overall, Agroforestry practices can reduce greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural activities. For example, the usage of cover crops and perennial vegetation in agroforestry systems can minimize soil disturbance, lowering emissions of nitrous oxide—a potent greenhouse gas. As communities face environmental challenges, maintaining agroforestry traditions can contribute to resilience by adapting to changing conditions while preserving cultural identity. The diverse variety of crops and tree species in agroforestry systems can improve climate resilience. Farmers who diversify their farms are less vulnerable to the ramifications brought on by extreme weather events, pests, and diseases. Further, agroforestry plays a significant role in land rehabilitation, offering sustainable and ecologically sound practices to restore

degraded lands. In agroforestry systems, the diverse variety of tree species and crops can increase resilience to climate variability. Farmers may reduce their exposure to the effects of pests, diseases, and extreme weather by diversifying their farms. In contrast to monoculture farming, agroforestry systems support higher levels of biodiversity. Various tree and plant species support a variety of organisms, increasing the resilience of ecosystems. Because biodiversity protects ecosystems from stress and change, it is essential for adapting to climate change.

In Tehri district, like other regions Garhwal, agroforestry practices has proved significant in combating climate change and enforcing land rehabilitation. However, there are numerous obstacles that affect agroforestry's success and broad adoption in India such as the lack of awareness and knowledge, access to quality planting material, financial constraints etc. Here, the adoption of the National Agroforestry Policy in 2014 becomes one prominent effort to eliminate most of the challenges. Moving the 2014 Policy from paper to practice remains a significant challenge even after it was adopted. Some policy gaps still exist, such as the lack of information about the chosen trees (there isn't an Agroforestry tree manual for farmers), the inadequacy of the certification processes for planting materials, the inadequate suggestions for incorporating biofuel into diesel and the creation of a specific Agroforestry extension system, and the lack of attention paid to novel and cutting-edge Agroforestry systems like Aqua Forestry.

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